

The male of the spiny-back orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) (Araneae: Araneidae)

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ABSTRACT: Only the female of the spiny-back orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) was known. Some information on the first male collected and photographed in South Africa is provided.

Key words: Afrotropical, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt, SANSA Virtual Museum, savanna, webs

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Afracantha* Dahl (1914) is a monotypic genus known only from Africa. The type species, *Afracantha camerunensis*, was described from Cameroon by Thorell (1899) as *Gasteracantha brevispina camerunensis*. The species is presently known from seven African countries: Cameroon, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Ghana, Eswatini, Botswana, Zambia, and South Africa.

Notes on the female were provided by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2021) and the first notes on their web behaviour by Heron (2017). The species is well camouflaged and not easily seen and is regarded as rare in South Africa, although single specimens have so far been recorded from three provinces in South Africa.

The first author (DP) observed the female of the species for the first time in her garden in Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal, in 2020, where she was able to photograph the female as well as the orb-web (Fig. 1) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). Now, for the first time, she has observed and photographed the much smaller male (Figs 3-4) with a female (Fig. 2) in her garden.

MALE DESCRIPTION

TL size 5.6 mm. The male resembles the female in colour but differs in size and shape. The carapace is dark brown, with numerous scattered strong, white setae. The eye region differs from the female in being narrowed anteriorly; lateral eyes close together, situated on carapace border but widely spaced from median eyes; anterior and posterior median eyes closely grouped; anterior median eyes on a small tubercle; posterior median eyes slightly wider apart. Abdomen is wider than long, with an uneven surface and with two prominent lateral humps with rounded, white distal tips. The humps differ in size with the posterior one being the largest. The carapace is brown with scattered orange, white, and dark patches. The integument with numerous strong setae of which the colour varies from white to reddish brown. Anterior edge rounded, dorsally bearing 14 dark sigillae. A double row of sigilla are arranged in rows medially. The legs are short and stocky and bear numerous clusters of the white, strong setae.

LIFESTYLE

On two occasions the orb-web of *A. camerunensis* was spotted in KwaZulu-Natal. The first was in a campsite in an open area of mown grassland dotted with *Vachellia* trees in the Umgeni Valley (Heron, 2017; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2021). The spider was suspended in a vertically oriented colourless orb-web with a diameter of about 20 cm and supported by a long bridge line about half a meter wide below an overhead branch of *Vachellia nilotica*.

Figures 1–3. *Afracantha camerunensis* from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal. 1. Orb-web. 2. Female. 3. Male. Photo credits: Desiré Pelser.

Figures 4–6. *Afracantha camerunensis* from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal. 4–5. Male. 6. Female, on bark, blending in with environment. Photo credits: Desiré Pelsler.

OBSERVATIONS

First sighting: The first sighting (March, 2017) of *A. camerunensis* was in the Umgeni Valley (Heron, 2017). The female was in an orb-web with two companion spiders, smaller in size. They were on both sides of the female but not in their own webs. The author later speculated that it might have been males.

Second sighting: The female was sighted in March, 2021, by the first author (PS) in an orb-web about 2.0 m from the ground in Kloof in KwaZulu-Natal (Fig. 1). A redescription of the female was provided by Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* (2021).

Third sighting: A female was photographed on 27 January, 2023 by the first author (DP) from the same tree that the second female was found in 2021 (Fig. 6). The female was seen the whole day and with the female was a very tiny spider that turned out to be the male (Figs 3–5). Below the web a bundle of prey debris covered with silk hang (Fig. 7). The purpose is unclear unless it is an egg sac covered by debris.

REFERENCES

- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., HADDAD C.R., FOORD S.H., LOTZ L.N. & WEBB P. 2022. The Araneidae of South Africa. Version 2: part 1 (A–C). *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide*, Irene, 74 pp. doi:10.5281/zenodo.6326922.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN A.S., PELSER D. & HERON H. 2021. Notes on the orb-web spider *Afracantha camerunensis* (Thorell, 1899) in South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae). *SANSA Newsletter* 38: 32–34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5947321>
- HERON H. 2017. Observations on *Afracantha camerunensis*. *SANSA Newsletter* 28: 10.
- THORELL T. 1899. *Araneae camerunenses* (Africae occidentalis) quas anno 1891 collegerunt Cel. Dr Y. Sjöstedt aliiq. *Bihang till Kungliga Svenska Vetenskaps-Akademiens Handlingar* 25: 1–105.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG. 2023. World Spider Catalog. Version 24. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on February 2023. doi: 10.24436/2

Figure 7. *Afracantha camerunensis* female from Kloof, KwaZulu-Natal. Photo credit: Desiré Pelsler